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Review Article

**ANALYTICAL METHODOLOGIES FOR DETERMINATION
OF TAMSULOSIN HCL AND TOLTERODINE TARTRATE IN
BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM**

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Shivnagar Vidya Prasarak Mandal's College Of Pharmacy, Malegaon BK(II), Baramati,
Pune-413115**Abstract:**

Tolterodine tartrate is an antimuscarinic or anticholinergic agent, It works by blocking a chemical that causes contraction of the bladder, It helps to reduce leaking of urine. This medication belongs to the class of drug known as antispasmodic. Tamsulosin HCL approximately 70% of the alpha-1-receptors in human prostate are of the alpha-1A subtype blockage of these receptors causes relaxation of smooth muscles in the bladder neck and prostate. The most commonly adopted methods for determination both drugs are HPLC (High Performance Liquid Chromatography), HPTLC (High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography), RP-UPLC (Reverse Phase –Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography) and UV-Visible Spectroscopy. This article provides critical review on the methodologies available for qualitative and quantitative determination of Tolterodine tartrate and tamsulosin HCL in bulk and Pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Keywords: Antimuscarinic, Tolterodine Tartrate, Tamsulosin HCL, RP-HPLC, UV-Spectroscopy, HPTLC, RP-UPLC.

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INTRODUCTION:

Tolterodine Tartrate is a potent Muscarinic receptor antagonist that is equipotent to oxybutynin in the bladder, but less potent in salivary glands with overactive bladder. [4]. Tolterodine is chemically designated as (R) -N,N-di-isopropyl-3-(2-hydroxy-5-ethylphenyl)-3-Phenylpropanamine L-hydrogen tartrate^[13]. Tolterodine has a high affinity and specificity for muscarinic receptor in vitro and exhibits the selectivity for the urinary bladder over salivary glands in vivo. The drug is listed in Merck Index . The empirical formula of Tolterodine Tartrate is C₂₆H₃₇NO₇ and it's molecular weight is 475.57 ^[2]. The Chemical structure of the drug Tolterodine tartrate was represented in Fig.no.1

Fig 1 : It Shows the chemical structure of Tolterodine Tartrate.

Tamsulosin hydrochloride is used to treat the signs and symptoms of benign enlargement of the prostate .chemically tamsulosin hydrochloride is known as 5-[(2R)-2-[[2-Ethoxy

phenoxy)ethyl]amino]propyl]-2-methoxy benzene sulfonamide hydrochloride and molecular formula of Tamsulosin hcl is C₂₀H₂₈N₂O₅.HCL and Molecular weight is 444.97.

The Chemical structure of the drug Tamsulosin Hydrochloride was represented in Fig.No. 2

Fig 2: It shows the chemical structure of Tamsulosin Hydrochloride

Reported Methods are categorized depending on the following consideration :

- 1) Methods for determination of Tamsulosin Hydrochloride Single and Combination with other drugs by UV-Spectroscopy, chromatography and other techniques.
- 2) Methods for determination of Tolterodine tartrate single and combination with other drug by UV-Spectroscopy, Chromatography and other techniques.

Sr. NO.	DRUGS	METHOD	DESCRIPTION	REF.NO.
1.	Tolterodine Tartrate	HPLC	Column : Thermo C18 (250×4.6mm) 5μ Flow rate: 1.0ml/min Mobile phase: Acetonitrile and Water(70:30) Detection Wavelength : 220nm Retention time: 7.1 min ± 0.1 min Tailing Factor : 1.43 % Recovery : 97.25% to 100.24% Regression Coefficient : 0.998 Linearity : 10-50μg/ml LOD : 1.52 μg/ml LOQ : 4.63μg/ml	20
2.	Tolterodine Tartrate	RP-HPLC	Column : Hypersil BDS C18 column Flow Rate : 1.8ml/min Mobile Phase : Solution A -Pot. Phosphate pH -4.5 and Acetonitrile mixed by low pressure Solution B - Acetonitrile and Water(70:30) Solution C - Pot. Dihydrogen Phosphate :Acetonitrile : Methanol : 40:60, 50:50, 60:40 V/V Detection Wavelength : 205nm Retention Time : 3.51 ± 0.0211 min Tailing Factor : 1.00 Regression Coefficient : 0.999 Linearity : 10.0 – 60.0 μg/ml LOD : 0.6 μg/ml	7

			LOQ : 10.0 μ g/ml	
3.	Tamsulosin + Deutasteride	RP-HPLC	Column : Kromacil ODS 3V (250 \times 4.6mm \times 5 μ) Flow Rate : 1.0ml/min Mobile Phase : Orthophosphoric buffer : Acetonitrile (65:35) Detection wavelength : 225nm Retention time : Deutasteride - 3.118 min Tamsulosin - 6.640 min % Recovery : 99.25% to 101.806 % Regression Coefficient : 0.998 Linearity : 5-15 μ g/ml LOD : Tamsulosin - 0.148 μ g/ml Deutasteride - 2.55 μ g/ml LOQ : Tamsulosin - 0.45 μ g/ml Deutasteride - 7.44 μ g/ml	10
4.	Tamsulosin+ Deutasteride	RP-HPLC	Column : Kromacil C18 Column(250 \times 4.6mm \times 5 μ) Mobile Phase : Acetonitrile: Methanol: Phosphate Buffer (40:30:30 V/V) Detection Wavelength : 223nm Retention Time : Tamsulosin - 2.653 Deutasteride - 4.693 % Recovery : 98.65% to 101.72% Regression Coefficient : Tamsulosin -0.9961 Deutasteride -0.9981 Tailing Factor : Tamsulosin - 1.195 Deutasteride - 1.241 Linearity : 19.2 – 44.8 μ g/ml	12
5.	Tamsulosin + Deutasteride	RP-HPLC	Column : C18 (4.6 \times 150mm \times 5 μ m) Mobile Phase : Phosphate Buffer (20%) pH Adjust 2.5 by using Orthophosphoric acid and Acetonitrile (80%) Flow Rate : 0.8ml/min Detection Wavelength : 274nm Retention Time : Tamsulosin - 2.003min Deutasteride - 5.067 min Linearity : 25 -125 μ g/ml Tailing Factor : Tamsulosin - 1.3 Deutasteride - 1.6	17

10.	Tamsulosin	RP-HPLC	Column : Intersil ODS 3V (5 μ , 15 \times 4.6mm) Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile + Buffer (30:70) Flow Rate : 2ml/min Retention Time : 6.618 min Detection Wavelength : 220 nm Tailing Factor : 1.099 % Recovery : More than 99% Linearity : 100-500 μ g/ml	18
11.	Tamsulosin	RP-UPLC	Column : Hibra C18 (100mm \times 1.8mm \times 2.6 μ) Mobile Phase : 0.01N KH ₂ PO ₄ (3.2 pH) : Acetonitrile (60:40) Flow Rate : 0.3ml/min Retention Time : 0.892 min Detection Wavelength : 224nm Linearity : 25 to 150 ppm Tailing Factor : 1.46 Regression Coefficient : 0.999 LOD : 0.039 μ g/ml LOQ : 0.120 μ g/ml % Recovery : 100.57%	19
12.	Tamsulosin + Tolterodine	RP-HPLC	Column : C18 (250mm \times 4.6mm \times 2.6 μ m) Mobile Phase : Column and Buffer (pH 4.0) : Methanol (60:40) Flow Rate : 1ml/min Detection Wavelength : 305nm Regression Coefficient : Tamsulosin – 0.9992 Tolterodine – 0.9965 Retention Time : Tamsulosin – 3.440 min Tolterodine – 5.693 min Linearity : Tamsulosin – 2-6 μ g/ml Tolterodine – 20-60 μ g/ml Tailing Factor : Tamsulosin – 1.348 Tolterodine – 1.243 LOD : Tamsulosin – 2.917 μ g/ml Tolterodine – 0.890 μ g/ml LOQ : Tamsulosin – 8.840 μ g/ml Tolterodine – 2.698 μ g/ml	11

13.	Tamsulosin + Tolterodine	RP-HPLC	Column : Hypersil BDS C18 (100×4.6mm, 5μ) Mobile Phase : Phosphate Buffer : Acetonitrile (65:35 V/V) Flow Rate : 1.0 ml/min Detection Wavelength : 220nm Retention Time : Tamsulosin – 2.285 min Tolterodine – 4.334 min Linearity : Tamsulosin – 1 -6 μg/ml Tolterodine – 10-60 μg/ml Regression Coefficient : Tamsulosin – 0.999 Tolterodine – 0.999 % Recovery : Tamsulosin – 98.40 % to100.42% Tolterodine – 98.16% to 99.76 % LOD : Tamsulosin –0.105μg/ml Tolterodine –0.859μg/ml LOQ : Tamsulosin –0.318μg/ml Tolterodine –2.603μg/ml	6
14.	Tolterodine	HPLC	Column : C18 (250mm×4.6mm, 5μm) Mobile Phase : Phosphate Acetate 0.1m (pH 2.5) : Acetonitrile (50:50V/V) Flow Rate : 1.2ml/min Detection Wavelength : 285nm Linearity : 10 to 100 μg/ml Regression Coefficient : 0.9942 % Recovery : 98.20% LOD : 5 μg/ml LOQ : 10 μg/ml	14
15.	Tolterodine	HPLC	Column : Phenomenex Luna C8 (250mm×4.6mm, 5μm) Mobile Phase : Methanol : 0.1% Orthophosphoric Acid in water (90:10) Flow Rate : 1.0ml/min Retention Time : 20 min Regression Coefficient : 0.999 Detection Wavelength – 220 nm	13
16.	Tolterodine	HPLC	Column : Inertsil C18 Column 3V (250×4.6mm,5μ) Mobile Phase : 3.85 gm Ammonium Acetate in 1L of water (pH 4.5 ± 0.05) using Glacial acetic acid and Acetonitrile (100% V/V) Flow Rate : 1.0ml/min Detection Wavelength : 290nm Linearity : 5-15 μg/ml Regression Coefficient : 0.998 % Recovery : 100% LOD : 1 μg/ml LOQ : 2.5μg/ml	2

17.	Tolterodine	UPLC	Column : BEH C18 Sub-2 μm acquity (100mm \times 2.1mm, 1.7 μm) Mobile Phase : Acetonitrile + Water (50:50 V/V) Detection Wavelength : 220nm Flow Rate : 0.3ml/min Retention Time : 2.60 min Regression Coefficient : 0.9992 % Recovery : 101.9 \pm 1.83 Tailing Factor : 1.14 Linearity : 20-60 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ LOD : 0.05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ LOQ : 0.15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	15
18.	Tolterodine + Tamsulosin	HPTLC	Column : Silica gel 60F254 backed on aluminium foil 20 \times 10cm Mobile Phase : Methanol :Ethyl Acetate : Triethylamine (5:5:0.3) Detection Wavelength : 220nm Linearity : Tamsulosin – 48-192 ng/band Tolterodine – 480-1920 ng/band Regression Coefficient : Tamsulosin – 0.999 Tolterodine –0.999 % Recovery : Tamsulosin – 98.83% to 99.44% Tolterodine – 99.19% to 99.39% LOD : Tamsulosin – 13.26ng/band Tolterodine – 22.44 ng/band LOQ : Tamsulosin – 44.34 ng/band Tolterodine – 74.85 ng/band	1
19	Tolterodine+ Tamsulosin	RP-HPLC	Column : Inertsil ODS C18 Column (150mm \times 4.6mm,5 μm) Mobile Phase : Phosphate Buffer + Acetonitrile (50:50 V/V) Flow Rate : 1.0 ml/min Detection Wavelength : 221nm Retention Time : Tamsulosin – 2.537 min Tolterodine – 4.660 min Regression Coefficient : Tamsulosin – 0.998 Tolterodine – 0.999 % Recovery : Tamsulosin – 98.5 % to 100.25% Tolterodine – 99.95 % to 100% LOD : Tamsulosin – 0.7 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Tolterodine – 1.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ LOQ : Tamsulosin –2.1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Tolterodine -3.9 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5
20	Tolterodine + Tamsulosin	Spectrophotometric	Mobile Phase : Methanol Linearity : Tamsulosin – 5-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Tolterodine – 10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Detection Wavelength : Tamsulosin – 221.5 nm Tolterodine – 234.0 nm Regression Coefficient : Tamsulosin – 0.9993 Tolterodine – 0.9988	9

CONCLUSION:

This review depicts the reported spectroscopic and chromatographic methods and validated for estimation of Tolterodine tartrate and tamsulosin HCL. In the present study it was concluded that for Tolterodine Tartrate and Tamsulosin HCL different spectroscopic and chromatographic method are available for single and combination with other drug. The mobile phase containing Acetonitrile, methanol, water, phosphate buffer were common for most of the chromatographic method to provide more resolution with flow rate in the range 0.3ml/min – 2ml/min.. For most claimed to be simple, accurate, economic, precise and reproducible in nature, Most of these methods were using RP-HPLC and UV absorbance detection.

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